

“THE MOST ADVANCED HUMAN REPRODUCTION TECHNIQUES IN THE WORLD IN ONE PLACE.”

Chedid-Grieco is a laboratory specialized in Reproductive Medicine that offers doctors and patients the most up-to-date technological resources in Human Reproduction. Our mission is to help infertile couples realize their dream of having children, at low costs and with maximum effectiveness. We serve health plans and work in partnership with specialist doctors.

"Chedid Grieco is a Miami, FL based reproductive medicine clinic that provides patients with the most cutting edge technological resources in reproduction and endoscopic surgery. Chedid Grieco is proud to offer infertile couples the possibility of realizing their dreams of having children. Call now for an appointment."

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